

Studies on Metal-Sulfur and Metal-Selenium Stretching Modes in the Complexes of Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Platinum(II) with Dibenzyl Sulfide and Dibenzyl Selenide

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Zinc(II), cadmium(II), mercury(II), platinum(II) complexes dibenzyl sulfide (DBS) and dibenzylselenide (DBSe) have been prepared and their structures have been characterised by means of various physicochemical methods including far infrared spectroscopy, electronic and $^1\text{Hn.m.r.}$ spectroscopy. Zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II) complexes are tetrahedral having the formula $[\text{M}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{M}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ whereas Pt(II)—complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ is square planar. $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBSe})\text{Cl}_2]_2$ is binuclear planar with chlorine-bridged structure. The $^1\text{Hn.m.r.}$ spectra of DBS and $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ indicate that $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ has a trans-configuration. The proton magnetic resonance spectrum $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ gives rise to only one phenyl peak at 2.8τ and a CH_2 peak at 6.45τ and a few small satellite peaks between 5.8τ and 6.2τ .

METAL-sulfur stretching mode of vibration has been the subject of much current research.

Since $\bar{\nu} = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{\mu}}$, this mode is proportional to the

square root of force constant K and reduced mass μ of metal and sulfur. Moreover, for metals such as Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) several conflicting reports are available in the literature concerning

$\nu_{\text{Zn-S}}$, $\nu_{\text{Cd-S}}$ $^{9-12}$ $\nu_{\text{Hg-S}}$ 13,14 . Since strength

of M-S bond naturally depends on nature of ligand, variation in the position of $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ bands is but natural. We have already reported¹⁵ our study of $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$ modes in case of Rh(III) and Ru(III) complexes of dibenzyl sulfide and in the present paper we are reporting our studies on Zn-S, Cd-S and Pt(II)-S stretching modes of vibration. By preparing and studying the complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pt(II) with dibenzyl sulfide and the corresponding selenium ligand — dibenzyl selenide, we have been able to make an unambiguous assignment of $\nu_{\text{Zn-S}}$, $\nu_{\text{Cd-S}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Pt(II)-S}}$ bands.

Materials and methods

All chemicals used were of chemically pure grade.

Preparation of ligands

Dibenzyl sulfide (DBS) and dibenzyl selenide were prepared in the laboratory and the products were analysed and their purity spectroscopically confirmed.

Preparation of metal-complexes

(i) *Trans-dichloro bis (dibenzylsulfide) Platinum (II)*, $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$:

An aqueous solution of potassium tetrachloro platinite (about 0.5 g.) was made methanolic and hot methanolic solution of dibenzyl sulfide (DBS) was added such that the molar ratio of DBS : $\text{K}_2\text{PtCl}_4 = 2 : 1$. Shaking was continued for one hour in order to ensure complete reaction and finally the reaction mixture was cooled in an ice bath when a brownish red precipitate of the complex $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was formed. The precipitate was washed with hot water, methanol and finally with ice cold ether, and the complex was recrystallised from benzene. It was dried in a desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 under suction.

Found : C, 49.0 ; H, 4.8 ; Cl, 11.9 ; Pt, 28.5%

Calc : C, 48.4 ; H, 4.1 ; Cl, 11.5 ; Pt, 21.9%

Colour : Brownish red. Melting point 53° .

(ii) *Chloro-(dibenzyl selenide) Platinum (II)- μ -bis-chloro-chloro-(dibenzyl selenide) Platinum (II)* : $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBSe})\text{Cl}_2]_2$.

This complex was prepared exactly in the same manner as the procedure given in (i) using K_2PtCl_4 : DBSe = 1 : 1.

Found : C, 30.9 ; H, 2.7 ; Cl, 12.8 ; Pt, 37.4%

Calc : C, 31.8 ; H, 2.6 ; Cl, 13.4 ; Pt, 37.0%

Colour : Brown. Melting point 130° .

(iii) *Dichloro bis (dibenzyl sulfide) Zinc (II)* : $[\text{Zn}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$:

About 1g of zinc chloride was dissolved in 30 ml of water and the solution was filtered. The

filtrate was treated with a few ml of methanol and 50 ml hot methanolic solution of dibenzyl sulfide (EBS) was added to it, such that molar ratio of metal ion : ligand = 1 : 2. The reaction mixture was refluxed on water bath for one hour. The little amount of precipitate first formed was discarded and the filtrate was cooled in a freeze when a pale yellow precipitate of the complex $[\text{Zn}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was formed. This was separated by filtration and the precipitate of $[\text{Zn}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was washed several times with hot water, methanol and ice cold ether to remove the excess of ligand. It was recrystallised from hot methanolic solution and dried by suction over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Found : C, 59.8 ; H, 5.3 ; Cl, 11.9, Zn, 11.8%

Calc : C, 59.5 ; H, 5.0 ; Cl, 12.6, Zn, 11.5%

Colour : Pale yellow. Melting point 164°

(iv) *Dichloro (dibenzyl selenide) Zinc (II)* : $[\text{Zn}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2]$:

This complex was prepared as described in (iii) using dibenzyl selenide as a ligand.

Found : C, 51.4 ; H, 5.3 ; Cl, 11.3 ; Zn, 10.4%

Calc : C, 51.1 ; H, 4.2 ; Cl, 10.8 ; Zn, 9.8%

Colour : Yellow. Melting point 260° (decomposed).

(v) *Dichlorobis (dibenzyl sulfide) cadmium (II)* : $[\text{Cd}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$:

Cadmium (II) complex was prepared by mixing an aqueous solution of CdCl_2 within 3% ethanolic solution of the dibenzyl sulfide (DBS) in a molar ratio of metal ion : ligand = 1 : 2. The mixture was digested on water bath for about 1 hour and filtered. The filtrate on cooling gave a white precipitate of the complex $[\text{Cd}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. It was filtered, washed with water, ethanol and ice cold ether. The complex was dried in vacuum desiccator over anhydrous CaCl_2 .

Found : C ; 55.5 ; H, 5.1, Cl, 11.9 ; Cd, 18.8%

Calc : C ; 55.0, H ; 4.6, Cl, 11.6, Cd, 18.3%

Colour : White. Melting point 216° , (decomposed),

(vi) *Dichloro (dibenzyl selenide) Cadmium (II)* : $[\text{Cd}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2]$

The complex was prepared as described in (v) using dibenzyl selenide as a ligand.

Found : C, 47.9 ; H, 3.8 ; Cl, 10.5 ; Cd, 15.6%
C, 47.6 ; H, 3.9 ; Cl, 10.1 ; Cd, 15.8%

Colour : Yellow. Melting point 94° .

Analyses : Microanalyses of the compounds were done at I.I.T. Kanpur. Analyses of metal ions and halogen were done by standard methods mentioned in the literature.

Infrared spectra :

The infrared spectra of these complexes were recorded in the range of $4000-250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ by means of Perkin Elmer 521 spectrophotometer using KBr pellets. Calibration was done with the help of a polystyrene film. The spectra of DBS and DBSe were recorded using their films.

Electronic absorption spectra :

Electronic absorption spectra of the ligands and complexes were recorded with the help of Hilger and Watts UV Spectrophotometer, model 700. The spectra were recorded in DMF and absolute alcohol.

Magnetic measurements :

The magnetic moments of the complexes were measured at room temperature on the Gouy Balance. Mercury tetrathiocyanato cobalt(II) [$\chi_g = 16.44 \times 10^{-6}$ C.G.S. units at 20°] was used as the magnetic susceptibility calibrant.

All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic.

Molecular weights :

The molecular weights of the complexes were determined cryoscopically. A standard Beckmann Freezing point apparatus with standard joints was used. The measurements were carried out in highly purified benzene using a Beckmann thermometer graduated to 0.01° .

Proton magnetic resonance measurements :

Proton magnetic resonance spectra of DBS and $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ were recorded using their CDCl_3 solutions with T.M.S. indicator.

Discussion

Micro analytical data indicate that all the complexes have the stoichiometry $[\text{ML}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ where $\text{M} = \text{Zn}(\text{II}), \text{Cd}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Pt}(\text{II})$ and $\text{L} = \text{Dibenzyl sulfide}$ or Dibenzyl selenide . Only platinum (II) complex with Dibenzyl selenide (DBSe) was found to have $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBSe})\text{Cl}_2]$ stoichiometry. All the complexes were found to be soluble in organic solvents such as CHCl_3 , acetone and ethanol and their ethanolic solutions were found to be almost non-conducting indicating that chlorine atoms are covalently bonded to the metal ions in these complexes. Molecular weights of $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Cd}(\text{II})$ complexes were found to be in agreement with

their theoretical molecular weight within 5% error. Pt(II)-complexes give abnormal molecular weights. All the complexes were found to be diamagnetic.

The major infrared bands of interest of the ligands and complexes are shown in Table 1. It has been observed by a large number of workers^{1-8, 20-22} that metal-sulfur bonding results in a red shift of the ν_{CS} band of the ligand. A perusal of Table 1 shows that in the complexes of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Pt(II) with DBS, the ν_{CS} band of the ligand (720 cm^{-1}) red shifts by 20 to 30 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the complexes (690-700 cm^{-1}). Thus DBS is coordinated to the metal ions through sulfur. Similarly, the ν_{CSe} band of the ligand observed at 615 cm^{-1} red shifts to 560-600 cm^{-1} in the complexes. This may also be taken as a proof of bonding of DBSe ligand to the metal ions through selenium.

in agreement with the positions of this mode described in the literature²⁴⁻²⁹.

Complexes of the type $[\text{PtLCl}_2]_2$ are generally dimeric⁴⁰. In view of this, it is suggested that the Pt(II)-complex with DBSe is atleast dimeric- $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBSe})\text{Cl}_2]_2$. One important proof for its dimeric nature is the presence of $\nu_{\text{Pt-Cl-Pt}}$ medium band at 400 cm^{-1} . Thus, the following tentative structure is suggested for this complex

C_{2v} Symmetry of $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBSe})\text{Cl}_2]_2$

TABLE I—MAJOR INFRARED BANDS OF INTEREST IN THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES(cm^{-1})

Compounds	ν_{CS}	ν_{CSE}	ν_{M-S}	ν_{M-Se}	ν_{M-Cl}	ν_{M-Cl-M}	Ref.
DBS	720 m	—	—	—	—	—	—
DBSe	—	615 m	—	—	—	—	—
$\text{Zn}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2$	700 m	—	340 w	—	330-3335 m	—	—
$\text{Zn}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2$	—	600 m	—	<250	<250	—	—
$\text{Cd}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2$	700 m	—	260 w	—	<250	—	—
$\text{Cd}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2$	—	560 m	—	<250	<250	—	—
$\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2$	690 m	—	315 w	—	372 w	—	—
$[\text{Pt}(\text{DBSe})\text{Cl}_2]_2$	—	560 m	—	<250	350 m	300 m	—
$\text{Zn}(\text{Q})_2\text{Cl}_2$	—	—	—	—	316,330	—	16
$\text{Zn}(\text{An})_2\text{Cl}_2$	—	—	—	—	294	—	17
$\text{Zn}(\text{Py})_2\text{Cl}_2$	—	—	—	—	308	—	18
$\text{Zn}(\text{SU})_2\text{Cl}_2$	—	—	—	<250	<250	—	19
$[\text{Cd}(\text{SU})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	—	—	—	<250	<250	—	19

DBS = dibenzyl sulfide, DBSE = Dibenzyll selenide,
Q = Quinoline, An = Aniline, Py = Pyridine,
SU = Seleno Urea, w = weak, m = medium.

A study of far infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes (Table 1) has been made to investigate the positions of metal ligand stretching frequencies. The present study indicates that $\nu_{\text{Zn-S}}$ is observed as a medium band at 340 cm^{-1} , $\nu_{\text{Zn-Cl}}$ at 330-335 cm^{-1} (m). $\nu_{\text{Zn-Se}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Zn-Cl}}$ are probably below 250 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $[\text{Zn}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2]$.

$\nu_{\text{Cd-S}}$ is observed at 260 cm^{-1} , $\nu_{\text{Cd-Cl}}$ is below 250 cm^{-1} . $\nu_{\text{Cd-Se}}$ and $\nu_{\text{Cd-Cl}}$ are probably below 250 cm^{-1} . $\nu_{\text{Pt-Cl}}$ (trans) mode is observed at 372 cm^{-1} as a medium band and $\nu_{\text{Pt-S}}$ (trans) is observed as a weak band at 315 cm^{-1} . On the basis of the positions of $\nu_{\text{M-S}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-Se}}$, $\nu_{\text{M-Cl}}$, tetrahedral structure may be assigned to the $[\text{Zn}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Zn}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, $[\text{Cd}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{DBSe})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ complexes. Since Cis-Pt(II) complexes^{20, 22} of the type $[\text{PtL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ give rise to a doublet bands below 330 cm^{-1} separated by 10 to 20 cm^{-1} corresponding to $\nu_{\text{Pt-Cl}}$ mode, trans square planar configuration is suggested to $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. The position of $\nu_{\text{Pt-S}}$ (315 cm^{-1}) is

The p.m.r spectrum of DBS shows its phenyl protons^{41, 42} at 2.8 τ and CH_2 protons at 6.5 τ and a complex small peak at 5.55 τ . The two CH_2 peaks may be due to staggered and eclipsed conformations of DBS. P.m.r. spectrum of $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ shows phenyl protons at 2.8 τ , CH_2 sharp singlet at 6.45 τ and small complex peaks in the region of 5.8-6.2 τ . This spectrum is quite different from the spectrum of cis- $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, reported by Jensen⁴⁴. The small CH_2 peaks may be due to eclipsed conformation of $[\text{Pt}(\text{DBS})_2\text{Cl}_2]$. Thus the p.m.r. spectrum of this complex suggests that it is a trans isomer which exists mainly in staggered conformation containing very small percentage of eclipsed conformation.

The electronic spectrum of this complex in DMF solution shows a peak at 30300 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon=1060$) corresponding to $a_g \rightarrow a_g^*$ transition and a weak broad shoulder at 20800 cm^{-1} ($\epsilon=40$) correspond-

NMR SPECTRUM OF $[Pt(DBS)_2Cl_2]$ IN $CDCl_3$.

ing to $b_{1g} \rightarrow a^*_g$ transition. The electronic spectrum of $[Pt(DBSe)Cl_2]_2$ is of different pattern.

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